

Proximate Composition of Time-Based Effects of Fish Feed Bioformulated with Unfermented Agricultural Wastes

Onwuka, C.N.

Department of Animal Production, Fisheries and Aquaculture, Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba, Delta State

Corresponding Address: onwuka.c@dou.edu.ng, +2348031317343

Received: March, 30, 2026; Accepted: June 5, 2026; Published: June 13, 2026

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20681698>

Abstract: Time-based effect of bioformulated feeds from agricultural wastes on proximate composition and nutritional value of feed was studied to determine percentage composition and nutritional value of crude protein, maize and wheat shaft, crude fibre, moisture, carbohydrate levels in formulated feed. Analyses were conducted to determine the material content of these feed materials. Result showed a significant difference ($P \geq 0.05$) in protein, moisture, and fibre, all in line with global nutritional requirements. The value highlights the potential inherent in biotechnology usage in feed formulation. Carbohydrate content ranged from 14.58 to 40.58%, crude protein ranged from 40.70% to 47.03%; moisture ranged from 10.20% to 12.74%; ash content ranged from 9.56% to 9.07%, crude fibre ranged from 10.75% to 12.75%; fat ranged from 11.50% to 11.50%. These values show a balanced nutritional profile to ensure stability and potential of nurturing fermented agro-waste as essential components in animal feed.

Keywords: *Agricultural waste, fermented waste, Time-based effect, Bioformulated feeds.*

Introduction

Tiamiyu *et al.* (2018) explained that agricultural wastes have supported increased production of animal's feeds, leading to increased food production.

Efficient management of agricultural wastes from soybean, maize, and bambara nut will lead to structural agricultural systems whereby waste is transferred into valuable resources (Chivenge *et al.* 2017). Also, Ogundipe *et al.* (2018) showed that unfermented wastes from agricultural products could serve on organic fertilizer to improve soil health and crop yield. Closely related, Nzayisenga *et al.* (2020) explained that animal feed, when incorporated with products from unfermented agricultural products, can help mitigate feed shortage and reduce feed costs in livestock production; Akinfemi *et al.* (2017) explained that Agricultural waste from maize, bambara-nut, and soya beans is rich in nutritional value, and is common in all our local communities. They are also of high quality and nutritional value, noting the high protein nature of the soya bean and carbohydrate value of maize. In all, Kumar *et al.* (2016) showed that simplified proximate composition will ensure balanced ratios promote growth and productivity. This research proposes a systematic of feed

formulation using agricultural by-products for increased production.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection, processing, and formulation of feed

The basic agricultural materials: maize, soya bean, wheat, and bone meal. These were collected from Ose-Marhek in Onitsha. Feed Formulation was conducted at Dennis Osadebay Food Mill in Asaba. The Feed material included white maize, soya bean, bambara nut, meal, grand nut cake, palm oil, starch, salt, vitamin premix five different rations were used for the experimental diet – 0%,25%,50%,75% and 100%, before taking them to the feed mill for processing into proper grinding, mixture, pelleting and drying

2.2 Proximate Analysis

The material contents of crude protein, fibre content, carbohydrate, lipids; moisture were determined using the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC), (2015).

2.3 Moisture Content

A petri-dish was washed and dried in the oven. Exactly 2g of each sample was weighed into the petri-dish. The weight of the petri-dish and sample was noted before

drying. The petri-dish and sample were put in the oven and heated at 100 °C for 1 hour. The result was noted, and then heated for another 1 hour until a steady result was obtained, and the weight was noted. The drying procedure was continued until a constant weight was obtained.

Calculation

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = W_1 - W_2 \times 100$$

Where:

W_1 = weight of petri dish and sample before drying

W_2 = weight of petri dish

Table 1: percentage composition of experimental diet.

S/N		0% Control	25%	50%	75%	100%
1.	Groundnut cake	41.00	35.50	20.00	15.00	12.50
2.	Fish Meal	20.00	25.50	20.50	9.50	4.50
3.	Bambara mitt waste	12.00	5.70	8.50	11.75	10.50
4.	Soya Beans waste	6.00	6.50	10.50	25.70	18.00
5.	Maize waste	8.00	6.30	11.50	14.00	22.00
6.	Vitamin C / Primix	1.50	1.50	1.50	0.50	1.50
7.	Blood meat	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.00	1.00
8.	Lysine	1.00	2.50	1.00	2.00	1.50
9.	Vegetable oil	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.55	2.00
10.	Starch	3.00	5.50	3.00	2.50	5.00
11.	Salt	0.50	1.50	1.50	0.50	1.00
12.	Wheat/Oak	4.00	6.50	19.00	16.00	20.50
13.	Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

2.4 Ash Content

An empty platinum crucible was washed, dried, and the weight was noted. Exactly 2 g of wet sample was weighed into the platinum crucible and placed in a muffle furnace at 500 °C for 3 hours. The sample was cooled in desiccators after burning and weighed.

Calculation

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{W_3 - W_1}{W_2 - W_1} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where:

W_1 = weight of empty platinum crucible

W_2 = weight of platinum crucible and sample before burning

W_3 = weight of platinum crucible and ash

2.5 Fibre Content

De-fat about 2 g of material with petroleum ether (if the fat content is more than 10%), boil under reflux for 30 minutes with 100 ml

of a solution containing 1.25% of H₂SO₄ per 100 ml of solution. Filter the solution through linen or several layers of cheese cloth on a fluted funnel, wash with boiling water until the washings are no longer acidic. Transfer the residue to a beaker and boil for 30 minutes with 100 ml of a solution containing 1.25 NaOH per 100 ml. Filter the final residue through a thin but close pad of washed and ignited asbestos in a Gooch crucible. Then, dried in electric oven and weighed. Thereafter, incinerated, cooled and weighed.

Calculation

The loss in weight after incineration × 100 is the percentage of crude fiber.

$$\% \text{Crude fiber} = \frac{\text{weight of Fibre}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

2.6 Protein Content

Exactly 0.5 g of sample was weighed into a 30 ml Kjehdal flask (gently to prevent the sample from touching the walls of the side of each, and then the flasks was stopped and shaken). Then 0.5 g of the Kjehdal catalyst mixture was added. The mixture was heated cautiously in a digestion rack under fire until a clear solution appeared. The clear solution was then allowed to stand for 30 minutes and allowed to cool. After cooling, about 100 ml of distilled water is added to avoid caking and then 50 ml was transferred to the

Kjehdal distillation apparatus. A 100 ml receiver flask containing 5 ml of 2% boric acid and indicator mixture containing 5 drops of bromocresol blue and 1 drop of methylene blue is placed under a condenser of the distillation apparatus so that the tap was about 20 cm inside the solution. The 5 ml of 40% sodium hydroxide was added to the digested sample in the apparatus and distillation commenced immediately until 50 drops get into the receiver flask, after which it was titrated to pink colour using 0.01 N hydrochloric acid.

Calculations

$$\% \text{ Nitrogen} = \frac{\text{Titre Value} \times 0.01 \times 14 \times 100}{\text{Weight of Sample}}$$

$$\% \text{ Protein} = \% \text{Nitrogen} \times 6.25$$

2.7 Fat Content

Dry 250 ml clean flasks in oven at 105 to 110 °C for about 30 minutes. Transfer into a desiccator and allowed to cool. Fill the flasks with about 300 ml of petroleum ether (boiling point 60 °C), plug the extraction thimble lightly with cotton wool and assemble the Soxhlet apparatus and allow to reflux for about 6 hours. Remove thimble with care and collect petroleum ether in the top container of the set-up and drain into a container for re-use. When flask was almost free of petroleum ether, remove and dry at 105 to 110 °C for 1 hour. Transfer from the

oven into a desiccator and allow to cool and then weigh.

$$\% \text{ Fat} = \frac{\text{Weight of fat}}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times 100$$

2.8 Carbohydrate Content

Carbohydrate content was determined according to the standard method of AOAC (2015).

$$\% \text{ Carbohydrate} = 100 - (\% \text{ Protein} + \% \text{ Moisture} + \% \text{ Ash} + \% \text{ Fat} + \% \text{ Fibre})$$

2.9 Statistical Analysis

Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and, the treatment means were separated from significance differences following the procedure of Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Steel and Torrie, 1980). All the analysis were carried out using the computer software Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Version 20 for Windows (SPSS, 2013).

3.0 Results and Discussion

Table 2: The result shows a significant difference in moisture content. The highest value was recorded in 100% (11.47), followed by 75% (10.85), 50% (10.83), 25% (10.77) and the control (8.47). For ash

content, there was a significant difference ($P > 0.05$) on 25%, 50% and 100%, but no significant difference between the control, 75%, and 100%. For crude fiber, no significant difference was observed among 50%, 75%, and 100%, but a significant difference was noted between the control and 25%. For fat content, a significant difference was observed among the control, 25%, and 50%, while no significant difference was found between 75% and 100%. Lastly, for carbohydrates, there was no significant difference between the control and 75%, but a significant difference was observed among 25%, 50%, and 100%.

3.1 Proximate composition

Table 2 show that the proximate composition of fish fed with formulated unfermented soybean, maize, and bambara nut waste changes as the level of unfermented waste increases. The moisture content progressively rises from 7.40% in the control to 10.74% in the 100UF (unfermented) treatment. Also, ash content increases slightly, as a result of mineral composition, more unfermented waste is being added, with values higher than those reported by Fasaki *et al.* (2015) for bambara nut.

Table 2. Proximate Composition of Formulated Feeds

Parameters	0%	25%(UF)	50%(UF)	75%(UF)	100%(UF)	P-value
Moisture	10.40±0.3 ^b	10.77±0.28 ^b	10.83±0.04 ^b	10.85±0.03 ^b	12.74±0.03 ^a	0.05
Ash	9.86 ± 0.06 ^a	8.81 ± 0.03 ^c	9.04± .04 ^{bc}	9.41 ± 0.11 ^b	9.02±0.05 ^{bc}	0.05
Crude Protein	47.10±0.15 ^a	33.49±0.04 ^d	34.59±0.02 ^c	35.41±0.12 ^b	40.71±0.07 ^b	0.05
Crude Fibre	10.75± 0.12 ^c	7.26 ± 0.22 ^d	11.67±0.17 ^b	11.83± .05 ^b	12.35± .06 ^a	0.05
Fat	11.35± 0.36 ^c	9.39 ± 0.08 ^d	13.74±0.21 ^b	14.45± .07 ^a	11.50± .02 ^c	0.05
Carbohydrate	14.50± 0.13 ^d	30.25± .39 ^c	40.21± .16 ^a	18.15± .15 ^b	40.58±0.06 ^a	0.05

However, the crude protein content decreases significantly, with the control group having the highest protein level. This contradicts the report of Anhwange *et al.* (2006), in line with Olanipekun *et al.* (2012) who stated that legumes typically have protein contents between 17% and 30%. There is also a noticeable increase in crude fiber content as the unfermented waste levels rise, with the (unfermented) treatment having the highest fiber content. Fat content shows a significant rise with the highest value in the (unfermented) treatment. On the other hand, carbohydrate content declines with increasing levels of unfermented waste. The control group has the highest carbohydrate content, while the (unfermented) treatment shows a marked reduction.

3.2 Moisture content

Moisture content of the samples ranges from 10.40 to 12.74%. This is in line with Jipara *et al.* 2021, who reported moisture content in feed ranging between 8.20 and 10.00%. The moisture content observed in this study falls within the desirable range, as Joshi *et al.* (2021) reported that higher moisture levels promote mold growth and feed decomposition, while lower moisture levels enhance the shelf life of fish feed. Among the samples, the (unfermented) treatment had the highest at 11.74% whereas the control exhibited the lowest moisture content at 7.40%. The (unfermented) treatment saw a significant increase in moisture (7.40%) compared to the control, while 50% and 75% showed minimal differences (10.77% and 10.83%). A significant difference was observed between the control and 100UF% treatments, while no significant differences were found

between the 25UF%, 50UF%, and 75UF% treatments.

3.3 Ash Content

This ranges from 9.86% to 9.02%. This shows the mineral composition in the fish feed, as the report of Solomon and Oyategbe, (2016) which had its ash content falling between 6% and 9%. It is known that these minerals contribute essential nutrients and assist in the breakdown of fats, proteins and carbohydrates. There was a significant difference in ash content between the 25UF, 50%UF, and 100%UF treatments, indicating substantial ash contents in this treatment. However, no significant difference was found between the control and 75UF treatments.

3.4 Crude Protein

Protein is an essential primary growth-promoting factor in fish feed. The protein requirement of fish is influenced by various factors: fish size, water temperature, feeding rate, the availability and quality of natural foods, and the overall digestibility of the diet. As shown in Table 1, the crude protein content in the feed ranges from 40.71 to 47.10%. The control treatment exhibits the highest crude protein content at 47.10%, while the 25UF% (unfermented) treatment has the lowest at 33.49%. This is probably due to the use of lower-quality inputs for

protein sources. For instance, bambara nut and soybean are legumes, whereas maize is a cereal. According to Anhwange and Atoo (2016), Bambara nut has a protein content of 18%, while soybean contains 40%. When combined with maize, which has a crude protein content of 8-11%, the overall protein content of the formulated feed can range from 30% to 48%. The results from this study indicate that the formulated feed using unfermented agricultural waste has a relatively low protein content when included in fish meal. This is consistent with the findings of Fasakin *et al.* (2015), who reported that *Clarias gariepinus* requires 40-45% crude protein in its diet for optimal growth.

3.5 Crude fibre

The crude fiber content, as shown in Table 1 ranged from 10.75% to 12.55%. The treatment with the highest crude fiber is 75UF (unfermented) at 11.83%, while the lowest crude protein content was recorded in 25UF (unfermented) at 7.26%. However, no significant difference was observed between the 50%UF, 75%UF, and 100%UF. In fish feed, the recommended crude fiber content is between 3-6% (Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO 2018, 2019). The values obtained in this study are relatively high; increased fiber content could aid digestion, but it should be moderated, as fish have a

limited capacity to digest fibrous material (Olaniyi and Onyenuga, 2013; Oyekale *et al.*, 2012).

3.6 Fats

The results presented in Table 1 show that the fat content ranges from 11.53% to 11.50%, with the highest at 0%UF (unfermented) at 14.56% and the lowest value observed at 25%UF (unfermented) at 9.36%. Joshi *et al.* (2021) reported that lipids/fats generally make up 10-15% of the feed, which aligns with the findings of this study.

3.7 Carbohydrates

The carbohydrate content in the table ranges from 19.86% to 40.58%, with the highest level observed in the 100%UF (unfermented) treatment (40.58%) and the lowest in the 75% UF (unfermented) treatment (18.15%). These results indicate that the carbohydrate levels in the feed are within the desirable range, consistent with the findings of Joshi *et al.* (2021), who reported that carbohydrates typically make up 20-30% of commercial fish feed. There was a significant difference in carbohydrate content between the control and 75%UF treatments, while the 25%UF, 50%UF, and 100% UF treatments did not show significant differences (Table 1).

4.0 Conclusion

The proximate composition analysis of fish feed formulated using unfermented waste from soybean, maize, and Bambara nut showed that agricultural by-products can be effectively utilized as sustainable and cost-efficient feed sources for aquaculture, thereby reducing feed cost. The waste materials provided a considerable amount of crude protein, fats, carbohydrates, and minerals, which are essential for the growth and health of fish. The feed also showed a low moisture content, enhancing its shelf stability and reducing the risk of spoilage.

It is recommended that fish feed production in Nigeria should be encouraged to adopt this fish formulation method giving its cost effectiveness, accessibility and nutritional balance. This will contribute to enhancing fish growth and production while reducing feed cost, and it will also help to ensure a balanced diet for different fish species and improve overall fish health and performance.

Government agencies, agricultural organizations, and aquaculture stakeholders should offer both financial and technical support through these simple methods to promote the adoption of time-based feed production to contribute to sustainable aquaculture practices and effective waste management in our local communities.

Acknowledgments

The Researcher acknowledges the immense technical and financial support given by Messrs Green Energy Foundation, led by Engr. Chief Chukwemeka Christopher Chukwurah, Green Energy Foundation (ECCCGEF). I am grateful.

References

- Akinfemi, A., Akinola, O. & Osunbitan, O. (2017). Proximate composition and nutritional evaluation of selected agricultural wastes in Nigeria. *Journal of Animal Production Advances*, 7(6), 333-340.
- Aniebo, A.O., Erondy, E. & Owen, O.J. (2009). Replacement of fish meal with maggot meal in African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) diets. *Revistacientifica*, 9(3), 666-671.
- Anhwange, B.A. & Ato, G. H., (2016). Composition of indigenous Bambara nut (*Vigna subterranean (L.) Verdc*). *Scary Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 2(1), 11-16.
- AOAC (2015). Official Methods of Analysis, 15thedn. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, 278 -28

Chivenge, P., Vanlauwe, B. & Six, J. (2017). Organic Inputs for Sustainable Soil Management: An African Perspective. *Sustainable Agriculture Reviews*, 28, 137-175.

FAO (2018). The state of the world fisheries and aquaculture. FAO fisheries and Aquaculture department Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Pp. 218.

FAO (2019). Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, the state of world fisheries and aquaculture. Rome; FAO Fisheries technical paper 500. 145pp.

Fasakin, E.A., Balogun, A.M., & Ajayi, A. (2015). The use of Bambara groundnut meal as a protein source in the diet of *Clarias gariepinus*. *Aquaculture Nutrition*, 21(2), 198-205.

Goyal A.K, Darzi G.N, Kumar A, Garg M, Singh I.P. (2019). Effect of fermentation on the proximate composition and functional properties of maize (*Zea mays*) flour. *Food Chem*. 114(3),1069-1076.

Jipara, P.H., Mormah, M.M., Zamaliah R. and Mohamed, K. (2001). Nutritional quality of germinated cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) and its application in home

- prepared powdered weaning foods. *Plant Food Hum. Nutr.*, 56, 203-216.
- Joshi, P.S., Praveen, B.M. & Aithal, P.S., (2021). Introduction to fish nutrition, feed formulation and feeding conversion. *Bioscience discovery*, 12(4) 208-216.
- Kumar, A., Gupta, V.K. & Verma, A.K. (2016). Management of Agricultural Wastes: An Approach for Sustainability. *International Journal of Recycling of Organic Waste in Agriculture*, 5(2), 72-81.
- Nzayisenga, L., Murekezi, A. & Mukandangwa, S. (2020). Assessing the Nutritional Value of Agricultural By-products as Animal Feed in Rural Settings. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 52(3), 1535-1545.
- Ogundipe, O.T., Olamide, O. & Adesina, I.O. (2018). The Role of Agricultural Waste in Sustainable Agricultural Production: An Overview. *Journal of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences*, 7(1), 45-58.
- Olanipekun, B.F. Otunola, E.T., Adejuyitan, J.A. & Adeyanju, J.A. (2012). Proximate and Fatty Acid Composition of Bambara Ground Nut (*Voandzeiasubterranean L. thouars*) as Influenced by Fermentation with a Combination of *Rhizopusoligosporus* and *R.nigricans*, *Transnational Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(9): 77
- Olaniyi, C. O. & Oyenuga, V.A. (2013). Influence of dietary maize and legume blends on the performance of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *International Journal of Aquatic Research*, 8(4), 145-153.
- Oshodi, A.A., Akande, G.A. & Oyewole, O.B. (2016). The effect of processing on the proximate composition, mineral content and functional properties of some Nigerian under-utilized legume seeds. *Food Chem.*, 34(1) 1-10.
- Oyekale, K.O., Daniel, M.O, Ajala, C.H. & Sanni, L.O. (2012). Potential longevity of maize grains under storage in humid tropical seed stores. *Nature and Science*, 10(8) 114-124.
- Solomon, J.R. & Oyategbe, O.H. (2018) Proximate analysis of *Claras gariepinus* fed with three local formulated fish feed. Article Number: DR JA386134792. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26765/DRJPHET.2018.4792>
- Steel, G.D. & Torrie, J.H (1980), Principles and Procedure of statistics. A Biometrical Approach. Second edition, New York: McGraw 633p.

Tiamiyu, L.O, Okomoda, V.T; Agbo, H.E
(2018): The Effect of Different Feeding
rates and restriction on the growth

performance of *Clarias gariespinus*:
Iranian Journal of Fisheries Sciences, 17
(4) 2018.